

SPECIFICITY OF THE SYMBOL AS AN ARTISTIC TOUCH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14020967>

Abstract. The article deals with the the problem of the symbol is the field of philosophical knowledge, the intersection of various points of view, philosophical positions, views. Symbolization is one of the most important ways for any artist-thinker to comprehend reality. In the process of working on a work, the author seeks to express the essential depths of the phenomena of reality reproduced by him, those depths that are obviously inaccessible to direct sensory perception and can be "captured" by the subject of perception only indirectly, through a kind of semantic analogy and through the corresponding emotional experiences.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается проблема символа как область философского знания, пересечение различных точек зрения, философских позиций, взглядов. Символизация - один из важнейших способов постижения действительности для любого художника-мыслителя. В процессе работы над произведением автор стремится выразить существенные глубины воспроизводимых им явлений действительности, те глубины, которые заведомо недоступны непосредственному чувственному восприятию и могут быть «схвачены» субъектом восприятия лишь опосредованно, через некую смысловую аналогию и через соответствующие эмоциональные переживания.

Key words: phenomena, communication, purpose, virtual, symbol, information, meaning.

Ключевые слова: явления, коммуникация, цель, виртуальный, символ, информация, смысл.

There are different versions of the origin of the word "symbol". Most researchers believe that it goes back to the Greek SYMBOLON and means "a conventional material identifying sign for members of a certain social group, secret society, etc." Russian poet of the Silver Age A. Bely believed that "symbol" comes from the Greek "sumballo", which means "connecting". German scientist-philosopher, one of the founders of modern hermeneutics and hermeneutic phenomenology G.G.Gadamer argued that the word "symbol" originally meant "document", "identifying sign", "certification". [44, p. 118] He is echoed by the French researcher P. Brunel, saying that originally this word implied a sign, thanks to which the guest introduces himself, a plaque, which he presents.

M.M.Kasperavicius explained the origin of this word as follows: “In ancient society the word ‘symbol’ denoted a certain joint action, a legal or political agreement, as well as a conventional sign showing belonging to a particular professional-religious grouping.

Symbols were used to designate draft ordinances drawn up at communal meetings ... In addition, the symbols were named passes for entertainment events, documents for receiving preferential bread from the state stores and Roman tessaries - manured boards on which military orders were written.” [89, p.Z] Rudolf Koch, author of an extensive study on symbols, states: “The word ‘symbol’ came into Western languages from the Greek word ‘symbolon’, which means ‘mixed in a heap’. The very concept of “symbol” was used to denote a meaningful image or meaningful sign, as well as ideas, feelings, and emotions. At the ancient Greeks such means served as shards of broken tiles, with the help of which people coming into contact could recognize each other, if the places of breakage at joining coincided, so every symbol is in its nature a secret or at least a conventional sign.” [100, p.G] The modern Russian researcher N.N.Rubtsov writes: “In translation from the ancient Greek symbol means ‘to connect’, ‘to merge’, ‘to bind’. The problem of the origin of the word “symbol” is not the subject of our study. We have cited several interpretations of different scholars only to emphasize the inherent diversity and ambiguity of this term.

The notion of “symbol” throughout the history of philosophical thought has caused many interpretations. In English literary studies, the interpretation of the symbol goes back to the works of Augustine the Blessed, who believed that the visible world is a symbol, a reflection of the Divine world, earthly attributes - a weak copy, a hint of the “Divine Ideas”.

The symbol is the meeting of the finite and the infinite. On the one hand, it is a product of our consciousness, on the other hand, it manifests the principles, ideas and meanings that exist independently of us and are inaccessible to our consciousness in their entirety. The concept of “symbol” is used extremely widely and seems, at a superficial glance, quite clear and understandable. But the matter is not so simple - this concept in different areas of spiritual culture is subjected to a specific analysis, in which the most diverse initial principles are possible and, consequently, the most diverse aspects of consideration of the symbol and its definition. As Y.M.Lotman correctly noticed: “We can say that even if we do not know what a symbol is, every system knows what ‘its symbol’ is and needs it for the work of its semiotic structure.” [121, p.P] It should be noted that we will consider the symbol in the system of culture, its functioning

first of all in literature. We will analyze the understanding of the symbol by philosophers and psychologists, as well as cultural scientists.

The uncertainty of its meaning and use is connected with the fact that the concept of “symbol” is similar to other concepts close to it, such as sign, allegory, metaphor. They are often intertwined, replacing each other. And quite often the symbol is understood and used as a conventional sign of any object or as a metaphor. Therefore, the concept of “symbol” is one of the most controversial and vague.

But, as noted by A.F.Losev, despite this, in the languages of all cultural peoples persistently preserved this term. Thus, the Greek concept of “symbol (symbolon)” as opposed to the concept of sign “semeion” or Latinized “signum” terminologically fixed the distinction between them, preserved in all European languages.

Throughout the development of philosophy and literary studies and in our time, thinkers who paid close attention to the symbol, noted its specificity and distinguished the symbol from similar concepts. For example, K.S. Stanislavsky singles out as the main features of the symbol organic integrity and naturalness, its ultimate brightness, originality and individual refinement, its multifarious content or inexhaustible semantic depth. [177, p.227-228] But the peculiarity, “otherness” of the symbol, fixed even in the language, did not prevent its understanding and use in culture, in scientific and artistic activities as a sign or trope. And first of all, we will try to understand why this happens and identify the specific features of the symbol. We will establish the difference between the symbol and other concepts similar to it.

Undoubtedly, both the sign and the symbol have formal and functional similarities. For example, from the point of view of A.F.Losev, who in his later works carried out a painstaking comparative study of the symbol and the sign, they differ only in the degree of generalization, when the symbol is a type of sign, extremely generalized signification. “The symbol is an unfolded sign, but the sign is also an unfolded symbol, its germ.” [118, p. 31-132] The distinction between sign and symbol, according to Losev, is determined by the degree of significance of the signified and symbolized object. This understanding of the differences between symbol and sign is very common and exists, for example, in modern semiotics; here also adjoins the idea that the symbol and the sign are only different degrees of vision of the world. But the criterion of significance is purely subjective in nature, depends on a variety of social and historical

circumstances, and therefore can not be considered the main and even the only one.

Insufficient distinction of the functions of sign and symbol in modern systems of scientific thinking leads to a lack of understanding of a serious problem associated with the fundamental differentiation of different types of consciousness and, consequently, different positions of a person in relations with reality.

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